

Stabilized Emotion – A Scientific Journey to Inner Fulfillment

By Miloš Večeřa

So if I ever receive money, fame, or recognition, I'll probably do this – give most of it away and keep only enough to share knowledge – for example, about chemistry. This is just like my great inspiration Michael Faraday, who also worked for others. And that's exactly what I want – not through imposition or expectation. Just by being. Some call it enlightenment, some wholeness, and others give it different names. I still don't know how to describe it scientifically. I just know that I don't need anything, not even hope that someone will recognize my research. And as young people would say – this is COOL! Yes, just COOL. And I'm only 35 years old. Already now I know I don't need anything! So yesterday evening, right before I went to sleep, the emotion stabilized – it just gently tickles. No mania, no panic that I have to do something. I just know one thing: when I go to London, I'll kiss the grave of my great inspiration, Michael Faraday.

So this is COOL! Becoming the youngest fulfilled person in history. :) This was pure science, no spiritualism, no meditation – and that's why it's COOL! :) I am no longer seeking proof, and I don't care how many anti-awards I get :). Everyone who knows me will understand – sooner or later :).